

1 **Bioethanol manufacturing from industrial olive pomace slurry through integrated**
2 **hydrothermal carbonisation and non-conventional yeast-based fermentation**
3 **processes**

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24 **Abstract**

25 The two-phase olive pomace slurry (TOPS) is the major waste of the olive oil industry.
26 Hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC) has been widely used for the conversion of TOPS into
27 hydrochar, a solid biofuel. The HTC process also co-produces a liquid hydrolysate, whose
28 valorisation has been scarcely investigated. This study focussed on to investigate the
29 composition (reducing sugars, total phenols, acetic acid and furfural) and use of the
30 hydrolysate derived from conventional and microwave assisted HTC of TOPS to produce
31 bioethanol by the fermentation carried out by *Hansenula polymorpha*, a non-conventional
32 yeast. On the basis of holocellulose content (39.12%) present in dry TOPS, the optimum
33 conditions to achieve a maximum reducing sugar yield of 25.92% through conventional
34 HTC were 180°C and 30 min. In the case of microwave HTC, the optimal conditions were
35 203°C and 30 min to obtain a maximum reducing sugar yield of 27.88%. The HTC also
36 produced total phenols (up to 3.30%), acetic acid (up to 3.33%), and furfural (up to
37 1.96%). In comparison to conventional HTC, the microwave HTC advantage was
38 generation of lower concentrations of fermentation inhibitors. The *H. polymorpha* strain
39 produced maximum overall bioethanol yield of 0.21 g·g⁻¹ in case of fermentation of liquid
40 hydrolysate at 45°C with inoculum concentrations of 0.8 g·dm⁻³. These findings
41 emphasised that the HTC of TOPS could be an alternative and promising method for co-
42 production of reducing sugars, bioethanol and total phenols.

43 **Keywords:** Olive waste; Hydrothermal carbonisation; High-temperature fermentation;
44 Non-conventional yeast; Bioproducts

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48 **1. Introduction**

49 The European Union (EU) is the leading producer of olive oil in the world, accounting
50 for about 2 million tonnes per year, or 68% of global output. Within the EU, the main
51 contributors are Spain (66%), Italy (15%), Greece (13%), and Portugal (5%) [1]. The
52 olive oil industry generates a huge quantity of olive pomace waste, about 800 kg per ton
53 of processed olive oil [2]. It is mainly produced as a by-product during olive oil
54 production through the milling of olive fruit followed mostly by malaxation and two-
55 phase centrifugation processes [3]. This olive pomace is commonly known as a two-phase
56 olive pomace, which contains on average 65% water content, 2–4% oil content, pulp, and
57 stones of the olive [4]. It also contains other useful constituents such as arabinose rich
58 pectin, about 30% potassium, oleanolic and masilinic acids [5]. The disposal of olive
59 pomace is a challenging issue for olive oil industry due to its acidic pH, high salinity, and
60 high phenolic contents causing phytotoxicity [2]. Valorisation of olive pomace for the
61 production of biofuels and other bioproducts will solve disposal problems and related
62 environmental issues [6]. This will also promote the biorefinery concept and support EU
63 member states to achieve the mandatory target of using 10% renewable energy in
64 transport (mainly including biofuels) in line with EU Renewable Energy Directive (EU)
65 2018/2001 [7].

66 The prevalent strategy for valorisation of two-phase olive pomace is to extract pomace
67 oil and prepare dried pellets of the remaining exhausted (de-oiled) olive pomace for
68 energy generation through combustion, pyrolysis and gasification processes [8–10].
69 Several industries have been using gasification and combustion of dried olive pomace for
70 power generation [11–14]. Application of pyrolysis technology for olive pomace has not
71 been implemented at an industrial scale. These are energy-intensive processes, which
72 requires the drying of wet olive pomace to evaporate high water content [8]. The solvent

73 extraction method was predominantly reported for polyphenols (mainly hydroxytyrosol)
74 extraction from olive pomace for application as antioxidants [15,16]. It was reported that
75 olive pomace contains 98% of the phenolic compounds of fruit, compared to 2% in olive
76 oil [17]. The utilisation of two-phase olive pomace was also documented for the
77 production of hydrochar, sugars, and bioethanol [18,19].

78 Hydrochar is mainly produced through the hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC), which is
79 a less energy-intensive method than pyrolysis and gasification due to the direct use of wet
80 biomass and the elimination of the energy-consuming drying step [20,21]. The HTC of
81 lignocellulosic biomass involved deformation and structural breakdown of the plant cell
82 walls which facilitated the hydrolysis of hemicellulose, partial hydrolysis of cellulose
83 (specifically amorphous cellulose part), and lignin rearrangement [22]. Wet biomass is
84 heated in a subcritical water condition for a few minutes to hours under 180–250°C
85 temperature and 5 – 20 MPa pressure [23,24]. During the subcritical conditions of HTC,
86 the hot compressed water decreases its viscosity and dielectric constant and increases the
87 water ionization constant. This led to water acting as an acid catalyst and an effective
88 solvent and reaction medium, which promoted the breakdown of biomass polymeric
89 structure [23]. In conventional HTC, the hot water and lignocellulosic biomass get heated
90 from the outer to the inner part due to heat transfer through a convection-conduction
91 mechanism. Therefore, the outer surface of biomass tends to have a relatively high
92 temperature [25]. Recently, the use of microwave (frequency range: 0.3–300 GHz)
93 assisted HTC reported to have more advantages such as direct non-contact heating, short
94 reaction time (≤ 50 min), and low heating temperature ($\leq 200^\circ\text{C}$) [26]. In microwave
95 HTC, microwave radiation transforms electromagnetic energy into heat, which causes
96 rapid and uniform heating of biomass [27]. The HTC of lignocellulosic biomass also co-
97 produces a hydrolysate (liquid fraction) rich in several by-products such as

98 hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), furfural, vanillin & phenols [28]. The composition of the
99 hydrolysate is highly variable and dependent on factors including temperature, holding
100 time, pressure, and pH of liquid medium. The longer residence time increased the severity
101 of HTC, which promotes the production of organic acids and the extraction of sugars in
102 the hydrolysate [20,29,30]. Earlier studies mainly documented phenol recovery from
103 olive waste using solvents, and conventional and microwave-based hydrothermal
104 extraction [15,16,31]. Olive waste (including olive pomace) was also reported for the
105 hydrochar production through conventional [31–40] and microwave-assisted HTC [41].

106 Bioethanol production from lignocellulosic biomass is very challenging due to its
107 recalcitrant structure and cellulose crystallinity [42]. Thus, enzymatic and acid hydrolysis
108 are used for the saccharification of lignocellulosic biomass to produce fermentable sugar,
109 specifically glucose [43]. Enzymatic hydrolysis (cellulase enzymes) is a common method
110 to hydrolyse the cellulosic fractions of biomass into sugars monomers (e.g., hexose,
111 pentose). Fermentation of simple sugars is conventionally done by *Saccharomyces*
112 *cerevisiae* yeast for bioethanol production [44]. The use of expensive enzymes and their
113 non-reusability makes enzymatic hydrolysis highly expensive. Biomass acid hydrolysis
114 also produces toxic & corrosive compounds that inhibit the fermenting yeast's activity,
115 reaction kinetics, and bioethanol yield [45,46]. Water-based hydrothermal pre-treatment,
116 commonly known as autohydrolysis, were reported for bioethanol production due to
117 advantages such as no use of environmentally polluting and corrosive chemicals (organic
118 solvents/acids), but the limitation was that sugar yield was found to be relatively lower
119 [47]. Several researchers studied combinations of autohydrolysis or dilute acid hydrolysis
120 and enzymatic hydrolysis of olive pomace to obtain fermentable sugar to produce
121 bioethanol [48–51]. Tayeh et al. (2014) reported that dilute acid hydrolysis of olive waste
122 at 100°C for 2 h produced a hydrolysate with glucose ($1.67 \text{ g} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$), xylose ($8.80 \text{ g} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$),

123 acetic acid ($2.13 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$), formic acid ($0.53 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) and furfural ($0.056 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$).
124 Enzymatic hydrolysis was also performed using cellulases and β -glucosidase mixtures to
125 obtain hydrolysate with more fermentable sugar. The hydrolysates were detoxified using
126 activated carbon to reduce inhibitor content and underwent fermentation by *Issatchenkia*
127 *orientalis*, which exhibited 3 g bioethanol yield from 100 g dry olive waste [52]. The
128 autohydrolysis of de-oiled olive pomace at 200°C for 30 min produced the hydrolysate
129 with $3.15 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ reducing sugar concentration. Subsequent enzymatic (Novozyme 188
130 and Celluclast 1.5 dm^{-3} enzymes) hydrolysis of solids obtained after hydrothermal
131 treatment generated 95.23% more reducing sugar content. The fermentation of this
132 hydrolysate by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* showed the bioethanol productivity of 0.086
133 $\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ [53]. The mixture of olive pomace and olive mill wastewater was pre-treated
134 at 120°C for 30 min with 0.5% H_2SO_4 to produce hydrolysate rich in glucose. The
135 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermented this hydrolysate after its lime pre-treatment and
136 produced a maximum ethanol concentration of $10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ [54].

137 The main focus of autohydrolysis of olive pomace has been to obtain hydrolysate rich in
138 fermentable sugar for bioethanol production. Details about the residual solid have been
139 seldom documented. In contrast to autohydrolysis, the goal of the HTC has been to
140 produce a hydrochar for several applications, such as biofuel and soil amendment [55].
141 The HTC process also produced a hydrolysate, which was seldom studied for bioethanol
142 production. In comparison to autohydrolysis, the integration of the one-step HTC method
143 and fermentation could be a better strategy because it has the potential to coproduce
144 hydrochar and a sugar-rich hydrolysate that could be used for bioethanol production. For
145 the first time, the present work evaluates this hypothesis for two-phase olive pomace
146 slurry. The HTC of two-phase olive pomace biomass produces solid (hydrochar), liquid
147 hydrolysate, and gaseous products. The detailed characteristics of hydrochar produced by

148 the conventional and microwave-assisted HTC were reported in our earlier publications
149 [39,41]. These studies reported the hydrochar yield on the basis of dried olive pomace
150 weight ranged from 50% to 90%. The higher heating value of the hydrochars were up to
151 32.2 MJ·kg⁻¹ suitable for biofuel application. In the present work, the gaseous products
152 were not collected and were retained inside the process reactors to maintain autogenic
153 pressure for HTC. For further advancement of fermentation research, the present study
154 also aims to investigate the *Hansenula polymorpha* yeast-based fermentation for the
155 production of bioethanol. *Hansenula polymorpha* is one of the non-conventional yeasts
156 widely reported for its high tolerance to temperature and inhibitors concentrations [56].
157 The novelty and specific objectives of the present work are: 1) To evaluate the
158 composition of hydrolysate including reducing sugars, total phenols, acetic acid, and
159 furfural produced by both conventional and microwave-assisted water-based HTC of two-
160 phase olive pomace slurry; 2) To assess the performance of *H. polymorpha* strains,
161 identifying best condition (inoculum concentration, and time) for fermentation of olive
162 pomace hydrolysate for bioethanol production.

163 **2. Materials and Methodology**

164 *2.1. Feedstock collection*

165 The two-phase olive (*Olea europaea L.*) pomace slurry (“Alperujo” in Spanish) was
166 obtained from the Almazara Andrés Aguilar, Linares (Jaén province), Spain. The olive
167 pomace slurry contained 80.43% moisture content, 28.30% hemicellulose, and 10.82%
168 cellulose [39]. In the laboratory, the raw material was stored in a freezer at -40°C to stop
169 microbial activity, gas formation, and biomass decomposition.

170 *2.2. HTC experiments*

171 The HTC experiments were conducted based on the face-centred central composite
172 design (CCD) with three central points prepared by response surface methodology, whose
173 details are provided in section 2.5. The CCD uses a second-order quadratic model based
174 on a minimum number of experiments to optimise variables and obtain the best response.
175 It is widely applied both in research and industries as an effective alternative to full-level
176 factorial design that requires a large number of experiments to study the impacts of each
177 variable on responses [57–59]. The CCD experiments were performed both by
178 conventional and microwave-assisted HTC methods with two factors i.e., temperature
179 (180°C–250°C) and holding time (2 min–30 min). Details of these methods were
180 described in earlier research publications [39,41]. The CCD with experimental and coded
181 values for HTC experiments was presented in Table S1 (Supplementary Information).
182 The conventional HTC experiments were undertaken in a stirred reactor (Parr 4848, Parr
183 Instrument Company, USA) with 2 dm³ capacity steel vessels. The microwave (1000 W)
184 assisted HTC experiments were done in a microwave digestion system (Milestone Ethos
185 One, Italy) with 10 closed vessels made of Teflon with each 100 cm³ capacity. Maximum
186 autogenic pressures (average values) were different during conventional (14.0 bars, 32.0
187 bars, 70.0 bars) and microwave (11.4 bars, 26.8 bars, 49.0 bars) HTC experiments at
188 180°C, 215°C and 250°C, respectively. The difference in pressure in conventional and
189 microwave reactors could be due to different ratio of volume occupied by the pomace to
190 free volume, amount of sample fed and steam generated. The solid and liquid phases
191 (hydrolysate) were separated after the experiment through the vacuum filtration method.
192 The liquid samples were stored in closed glass bottles in a deep freezer at –40°C to
193 minimise the degradation of organic compounds. The abbreviations for samples produced
194 under different conditions are C_x–y or M_x–y, where C and M indicate conventional or

195 microwave reactors, respectively, x is the temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and y is the holding time
196 (min).

197 2.3. Fermentation experiments

198 The wild-type *Hansenula polymorpha* yeast strain (DSM 70277) was acquired from the
199 Leibniz Institute, DSMZ-German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH
200 in Braunschweig, Germany. It was conserved in the autoclaved solid agar media
201 composed of $3\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ yeast extract; $3\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ malt extract; $5\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ peptone; $10\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
202 xylose; and $20\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ agar-agar [60]. Then, an adapted strain was prepared by the
203 adaptive evolution method [61]. This involved growing the wild-type strain in a 50 cm^3
204 conical flask sealed with a cotton plug and containing 25 cm^3 nutrient medium and diluted
205 hydrolysate mixture for 48h at 35°C in a thermostat shaker (IKA INC 125 FS Digital,
206 Spain). The liquid medium was made of by mixing $2.0\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ yeast extract, $1.8\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
207 peptone, $1.5\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, $1.0\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ $\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $1.0\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ KH_2PO_4 in
208 distilled water [62]. A 0.25 cm^3 aliquot was transferred to new flasks with a gradual
209 increase in concentration of hydrolysate. This process was repeated multiple times (20
210 cycles) to prepare an adapted strain of *H. polymorpha* to improve its growth in the
211 hydrolysate.

212

213 The adapted strain was used for the fermentation of hydrolysate to produce bioethanol,
214 and xylitol. The fermentation experiments were conducted in aforesaid thermostat shaker
215 using 250 cm^3 conical flasks with caps and provisions to collect samples periodically
216 through syringes. Experiments were performed for different inoculum concentrations (0.1
217 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ to $1.3\text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$), temperatures (35°C to 45°C), and time (0 h to 92.5 h). The CCD
218 with experimental and coded values for fermentation experiments was presented in Table
219 S2 (Supplementary Information). A fixed pH of 5.5 and a mixture of 75% concentrated

220 hydrolysate and 25% nutrient media were used for the fermentation. External aeration
221 was not provided during the experiment. The yeasts were dependent on the dissolved
222 oxygen ($3.81 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) present in the hydrolysate. The spectrophotometric method was
223 used for estimating the yeast biomass concentration ($\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) on the basis of a calibration
224 curve prepared using the optical density value (620 nm) and yeast biomass oven-dried
225 weight (g). The concentrations of dissolved oxygen (DO) in the fermentation medium
226 were determined with the optical dissolved oxygen instrument (HI-98198, Hanna
227 Instruments Ltd., UK).

228

229 The maximum specific growth rate and volumetric productivity of the yeast were
230 calculated using Equations (1) and (2), respectively. In Equation (1), ' μ_m ' is maximum
231 rate of specific growth, h^{-1} ; ' x ' is cell concentration per volume at varied time (t); ' x_0 ' is
232 cell concentration at the initial time (t=0); ' a ' is empirical constant that represents the
233 change in growth rate with time. The ' μ_m ' and ' a ' are the values of slope and intercept
234 respectively, derived from the linear plot between ' t ' and ' $\ln(x/x_0)$ ' for exponential
235 growth phase. In Equation (2), ' P_b ' is volumetric productivity ($\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$), and ' c ' is
236 empirical constant for relation between volumetric productivity and time [60,63]. The
237 empirical constants are numerical values derived from experimental data to fit the
238 equation and calculate the desired parameters such as μ_m and P_b .

$$\ln\left(\frac{x}{x_0}\right) = \mu_m t + a \quad (1)$$

$$x = c + P_b t \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{x/s}^o = \frac{dx}{d(s_0 - s)} \quad (3)$$

239 Overall biomass yield ($Y_{x/s}^0$), measured as per Equation (3), is a quotient among net
 240 biomass produced and net substrate uptake. In this equation, $Y_{x/s}^0$ is slope value, calculated
 241 based on the values of $x - x_0$ versus $s_0 - s$ [60].

242 The specific substrate (TRS) uptake rate (q_s) was determined transforming the Equation
 243 (4) in linear form and performing least square adjustments. Where 's' is the substrate
 244 uptake at a definite time; 's₀' is the substrate uptake at starting time (t = 0); 'α' and 'β'
 245 are empirical constants indicated the change in substrate uptake rate with time. The
 246 specific ethanol production rate (q_{et}) is calculated by differential treatment of the kinetic
 247 linear Equation (5), where x_{et} is bioethanol concentration, 'a' and 'b' are empirical
 248 constants representing the change in ethanol production with time. The overall bioethanol
 249 yield (Y_{et}^0) was calculated using Equation (6) [60]. In Equation (6), e_t = bioethanol
 250 concentration; Y_{et}^0 is overall bioethanol yield calculated from the values of $e_t - e_0$ (t = 0)
 251 versus s_0 (t = 0) - s. Similarly, instantaneous product yield (Y_{et}) is determined using the
 252 values of $e_t - e_0$ (t = 0) versus $x - x_0$ (t = 0).

$$s = s_0 \alpha^{-t^\beta} \quad (4)$$

$$x_{et} = a + b \cdot t \quad (5)$$

$$Y_{et}^0 = \frac{d_{et} - d_{et \text{ at } 0}}{d(s_0 - s)} \quad (6)$$

253 2.4. Analysis of liquid samples

254 Miller's method (1959) was used to analyse total reducing sugar (TRS) in hydrolysates,
 255 with dinitrosalicylic acid reagent [64]. The monosaccharides concentrations were
 256 measured using an ion chromatograph equipped with a Metrosep Carb 2 100/4.0 IC
 257 column (Carb 2 150/4.0) and a pulsed amperometric detector (930 Compact IC Flex,

258 Metrohm AG, Switzerland). The aforementioned sugar were acquired from Sigma
259 Aldrich (Merck, Germany) and utilised to create the calibration curve. The eluent for ion
260 chromatography was a mixture of 100 mM NaOH and 10 mM sodium acetate solution
261 provided by Metrohm AG (Herisau, Switzerland). Acetic acid was tested using an
262 enzymatic method (Enzytec™ Liquid Acetic Acid E8226, R-Biopharm AG, Germany).
263 Total phenols were determined spectrophotometrically using the Folin-Calcateu reagent
264 and expressed as gallic acid equivalent [65]. The ethanol concentrations were determined
265 using gas chromatography (Shimadzu 2010 Plus, Japan) with an FID detector and BPX5
266 capillary column. Helium was employed as a carrier gas, with a flow rate of 50 cm³min⁻¹.
267 Sample analysis was carried out using an external bioethanol (GC standard, Sigma
268 Aldrich, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) for the calibration, an analytical column
269 temperature of 55 °C, a pressure level of 100 kPa, and an oven temperature of 70°C.
270 Xylitol concentrations were determined using an enzymatic test (Cat. No. 10670057035;
271 R-BIOPHARM, Germany).

272 2.5. Response surface design analysis

273 Modde 6.0 software (Umetric AB, Sweden) was used to prepare CCD for HTC and
274 fermentation, and subsequent data analysis on the basis of a second-order polynomial
275 model (Equation - 7) involving two independent variables (IV_1 and IV_2) and responses
276 (Yield for TRS, total phenols, and ethanol). The independent variables (IV_1 and IV_2) were
277 temperature (T) and holding time (t), respectively, for HTC experiments; while for
278 fermentation assays IV_1 was the inoculum concentration (IC) and IV_2 was the bioprocess
279 time (t).

$$Y = \beta_0 + (\beta_1 \cdot IV_1) + (\beta_2 \cdot IV_2) + (\beta_3 \cdot IV_1 \cdot IV_1) + (\beta_4 \cdot IV_2 \cdot IV_2) + (\beta_5 \cdot IV_1 \cdot IV_2) \quad (7)$$

280 where Y is the response value, IV_1 and IV_2 are the real values of the two independent
281 variables, and β_i ($i = 1-5$) are the intercept term (β_0), the linear effects (β_1 and β_2), the
282 squared effects (β_3 and β_4), and the interaction effects (β_5) calculated from the
283 experimental data by regression analysis. The experimental data validation was
284 performed by a one-way ANOVA statistical test with a 95% confidence level.

285 **3. Results and Discussions**

286 *3.1. Reducing sugar production*

287 The average values (with standard deviations) for TRS contents, its conversion yield
288 (based on holocellulose fraction of dried olive pomace), and concentrations of glucose,
289 fructose, xylose, sucrose, and lactose present in the hydrolysate produced by conventional
290 and microwave-assisted HTC of olive pomace slurry are presented in Table S3
291 (Supplementary information). In addition, the TRS contents and its conversion yields for
292 HTC samples are also shown in Figure 1. The HTC and treatment conditions (temperature
293 and holding time) impacted the generation of TRS. The variations were also observed for
294 TRS between hydrolysates produced by microwave and conventional HTC at same
295 temperatures and holding time. This could be due to their non-uniform autogenic
296 pressures (mentioned in section 2.2). In contrast to microwave HTC, the autogenic
297 pressures were relatively higher in conventional HTC due to conduction-convection
298 heating mechanism and use of larger reactor vessel. It influenced the HTC process
299 severity and several simultaneous reactions such as hydrolysis of polysaccharides and
300 oligosaccharides into TRS, and its transformation into organic acids and furfural. When
301 the HTC temperature reaches 180°C, the hemicellulose depolymerizes into
302 oligosaccharides by proton-catalysed cleavage of glycosidic bonds, which hydrolyse into
303 glucose, fructose, and other monosaccharides (e.g., hexoses, pentoses, etc.). The
304 amorphous cellulose fractions depolymerise above 210°C, resulting in oligosaccharides

305 and cellobiose, which are subsequently hydrolysed to produce monosaccharides such as
306 glucose and fructose. The crystalline cellulose remains resistant to hydrolysis by hot
307 compressed water [75]. A balance between degradation and hydrolysis reactions during
308 HTC is necessary to achieve higher TRS yields. The concentrations of TRS (per g dry
309 olive pomace) were generally higher in the hydrolysate produced by microwave HTC
310 ($49.44 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ – $107.13 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) than conventional HTC ($40.54 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ – $101.20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). In
311 comparison to present results, Yuan et al. (2019) also found TRS yields of $118.57 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$
312 to $120.33 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ from tobacco waste (leaf and stem) by microwave-assisted hydrothermal
313 treatment [66]. The conversion yields for TRS based on the dried weight of olive pomace
314 were 4.94%–10.71% and 4.05%–10.12%, whereas based on holocellulose content
315 (39.12%) of olive pomace, TRS conversion yields were 12.64%–27.38% and 10.36%–
316 25.87% for microwave HTC and conventional HTC, respectively. The influence of
317 holding time on TRS was observed to be different at specific HTC temperatures. The TRS
318 yields increased with prolongation of holding time from 2 min to 30 min for microwave
319 HTC at 180°C and 215°C, and for conventional HTC at 180°C. In contrast, TRS yields
320 reduced with an increase in holding time at 250°C with microwave HTC and at 215°C
321 and 250°C with conventional HTC. The maximum TRS yield was 25.87% in case of
322 conventional HTC at 180°C for 30 min. Comparatively, the microwave HTC at 215°C
323 for 30 min produced more TRS yield (27.38%).

324

325 Figure 1. TRS contents in the hydrolysate and conversion yields of TRS on basis of
 326 holocellulose content of dried olive pomace for samples produced by microwave and
 327 conventional HTC.

328 The concentrations of glucose, fructose, lactose, xylose, and sucrose on basis of dried
 329 olive pomace are presented in Figure 2. The maximum concentrations of glucose were
 330 in M215-16 (5.98 mg·g⁻¹), fructose in C250-2 (8.18 mg·g⁻¹), sucrose (2.86 mg·g⁻¹) and
 331 xylose (2.65 mg·g⁻¹) in C180-30, and lactose (3.98 mg·g⁻¹) in M250-2 hydrolysates. The
 332 microwave HTC from 180°C-2 min to 215°C-16 min resulted into enrichment of glucose
 333 concentrations (2.97 mg·g⁻¹–5.98 mg·g⁻¹). The glucose concentrations were 36.95%
 334 higher with microwave HTC at 215°C-16 min compared to maximum glucose
 335 concentration of 3.77 mg·g⁻¹ obtained with conventional HTC at 180°C for 2 min. Fan et
 336 al. (2013) also reported that microwave-assisted hydrothermal treatment of cellulose
 337 yielded 1.2% more glucose obtained with conventional HTC at 220°C [76]. However,
 338 microwave HTC post 215°C-16 min and conventional HTC post 180-2 min treatment
 339 conditions exhibited decreasing trend for the glucose concentrations. But the fructose
 340 concentrations were elevated in those conditions and the glucose concentrations

341 diminished specifically in M250-16, M250-30, C215-2, C215-16, C215-30, C250-2,
 342 C250-16 and C250-30. This difference could be due to the isomerization of glucose into
 343 fructose during those HTC conditions [67,68]. The isomerization can take place by two
 344 pathways, based on Brønsted base catalysis (also known as Lobry de Bruyn-van
 345 Ekenstein rearrangement) [69,70] and Lewis acid catalysis [71]. The first pathway
 346 involved the interaction of the glucose with a Brønsted base (as a proton acceptor) that
 347 formed a 1,2-enediol intermediate. Thereafter, subsequent transfer of a proton from O-2
 348 to O-1 and C-2 to C-1 led to fructose formation. In the case of the second pathway, the
 349 Lewis acid sites, with the help of their lone electron pair, interacted with O-1 of the
 350 glucose and polarized the C=O bond. The same acid sites engaged with the O-2 atom,
 351 which created a complex and caused a shift of intramolecular hydrogen from C-2 to C-1,
 352 resulting in the fructose production [72–74]. The formation of Lewis acids (phenols and
 353 acetic acids) in hydrolysate and their cumulative impact during HTC could be the reason
 354 for isomerisation of glucose to fructose, observed in this study. However, to support this
 355 reason more detailed study on specific mechanisms are required.

356

357 Figure 2. Concentrations of glucose, fructose, sucrose, xylose and lactose in the
358 hydrolysate samples produced by microwave and conventional HTC.

359 *3.2. Total phenols, acetic acid and furfural production*

360 The concentrations of total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural in the hydrolysate produced
361 by the conventional and microwave HTC are shown in Figure 3. Total phenols were
362 inherently present in the slurry of the olive pomace, which increased further specifically
363 at higher HTC temperature due to depolymerization of lignin. Acetic acid was formed
364 from the cleavage of acetyl groups in hemicellulose fractions (Li et al., 2015) and furfural
365 was formed due to the thermal dehydration of saccharides (specifically pentoses like
366 xylose) during HTC [77]. In general, the HTC in a microwave reactor generated relatively
367 lower total phenols (1.66%–2.88%), acetic acid (0.27%–2.09%), and furfural contents
368 (0.08%–0.33%) than conventional HTC (1.24%–3.30% total phenols, 0.54%–3.33%
369 acetic acid, 0.20%–1.96% furfural). Increasing the HTC temperature from 180°C to
370 250°C resulted in the production of more total phenols, acetic acid, and furfural. The
371 escalation in HTC holding time from 2 min to 30 min at specific temperatures enhanced
372 the formation of furfural. However, there was a non-uniform impact of holding time on
373 the total phenols and acetic acid. The use of a conventional pressure reactor produced
374 higher total phenols (3.30%) at 250°C-2 min, acetic acid (3.33%) at 250°C-30 min, and
375 furfural (1.96%) at 250°C-30 min. In the case of the microwave reactor, maximum
376 concentrations of total phenols (2.88%) were generated at 250°C-30 min, acetic acid
377 (2.09%) at 250°C-2 min, and furfural (0.37%) at 250°C-30 min. Formation of acetic acid
378 led to a decrease in pH from 5 (two-phase olive pomace slurry) to 3 (hydrolysate from
379 HTC).

380 Phaiboonsilpa et al. (2020) also documented that hydrothermal treatment at a higher
381 temperature of 250°C produced more organic acids and furfural formed by the

382 decomposition of xylose, oligosaccharides, glucose, and arabinose [78]. During HTC, the
383 lignin undergoes hydrolysis, partial cleavage of β -O-4, ether bonds, aliphatic C–C bonds
384 cleavage, alkylation, and demethoxylation. The lignin depolymerizes above 210°C into
385 an aromatic oligomer, and its hydrolysis produces phenol compounds and methoxylated
386 benzenes. The hydrolysate of lignin contained phenol, cresol, catechol, and guaiacol. An
387 increase in temperature causes more production of alkyl-substituted phenols from
388 methoxyl aromatic products [79,80]. In contrast to the present results, Gimenez et al.
389 (2020) reported a higher total phenols content of 3.58% in hydrolysate obtained from
390 HTC of two-phase olive pomace at 240°C for 4h. This difference was due to the use of
391 longer residence time for HTC. Generally, hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol were the main
392 phenolic compounds found in the olive pomace hydrolysate [31]. Overall, the
393 experimental results highlighted that microwave HTC was suitable for obtaining
394 relatively higher TRS and lower contents of inhibitors (total phenols, acetic acid, and
395 furfural). However, the conventional HTC was found more suitable for more
396 transformation of sugar to acetic acid and furfural.

397

398

399

400 Figure 3. Total phenols, acetic acid and furfural concentrations in the hydrolysate samples
 401 produced by the microwave and conventional HTC.

402 3.3. Fermentation of hydrolysate

403 3.3.1 DO consumption

404 The consumption of DO after 92.5 h fermentation of hydrolysate and pure sugars (glucose
 405 and xylose in 1:1 ratio) by wild type and adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* are shown in
 406 Figure 4. Adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* were obtained through adaptive evolution
 407 using hydrolysate. The DO consumption by adapted *H. polymorpha* strains were
 408 relatively lower (75.7%) in fermentation of hydrolysate with 1.3 g·dm⁻³ inoculum at 40°C
 409 and 0.8 g·dm⁻³ inoculum at 35°C. Increasing the fermentation temperature from 35°C to
 410 40°C, accelerated the DO consumption from 75.7% to 84.9%, but further increase of
 411 fermentation temperature to 45°C reduced the DO consumption to 83.3%. The inoculum
 412 of 0.1 g·dm⁻³ adapted strain showed the highest DO consumption of 95.7% in case of
 413 fermentation of pure sugars. Whereas, in same conditions for fermentation of hydrolysate,
 414 the DO consumption was 91.2%. The use of low inoculum concentration (0.1 g·dm⁻³)

415 exhibited more DO consumption compared to high inoculum $81.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$). The
 416 consumption of DO for fermentation of hydrolysate by wild type strain was relatively
 417 higher (90.0%) than adapted strain (84.9%). Overall, the above results exhibited the
 418 ability of *H. polymorpha* strain under limited oxygen presence, which is in agreement
 419 with previous studies [60,81].

420
 421 Figure 4. Average values of DO consumption by *H. polymorpha* strains under different
 422 fermentation conditions. Adapted strain led fermentation at 40°C with: a) $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
 423 inoculum, b) $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum, c) $1.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in hydrolysate and, d) 0.1
 424 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in pure sugar (glucose+xylose); e) $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in hydrolysate
 425 at 35°C fermentation; f) wild type strain with $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in hydrolysate at 40°C ;
 426 g) wild type strain with $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in pure sugar (glucose+xylose) at 40°C ; h)
 427 Adapted strain with $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum in hydrolysate at 45°C .

428 3.3.2 Yeast growth and production of bioethanol

429 Bioethanol is produced by yeast from glucose and xylose through two different pathways.
 430 The glucose is biologically converted into bioethanol through the Embden–Meyerhof–
 431 Parnas pathway. On the other hand, xylose is first converted to xylulose, and it is
 432 converted into bioethanol through the pentose phosphate pathway [82]. In this study, *H.*

433 *polymorpha* was selected for bioethanol production because it is a thermotolerant yeast
434 and favours the fermentation of varied sugars such as glucose, xylose and cellobiose. The
435 *H. polymorpha* developed tolerance to high temperature (up to 50°C) due to synthesis and
436 accumulation of trehalose, a thermo-protective compound [83]. It is also resistant to
437 inhibitors present in the hydrolysate [84]. The application of the adaptive evolution
438 method was done to make *H. polymorpha* more inhibitor-resistant. The hydrolysate used
439 for fermentation contained about 22.79 g·dm⁻³ of TRS, 1.80 g·dm⁻³ of total phenols, 0.64
440 g·dm⁻³ of furfural, and 1.29 g·dm⁻³ of acetic acid. Figure 5 presents the influence of
441 fermentation parameters on the growth of the adapted *H. polymorpha* strain. The
442 temperature, inoculum concentrations, and time impacted the performance of the adapted
443 yeast strain, fermentation process, and bioethanol production (Table 1). In addition to
444 bioethanol, the xylitol was also coproduced at 20 h fermentation time, 0.06 g·dm⁻³ with
445 pure sugar, and with hydrolysate ranged from 0.03 g·dm⁻³ to 0.04 g·dm⁻³.

446

447 Figure 5. Growth curve (based on average values) of adapted *H. polymorpha* with a)
 448 different inoculum concentrations and b) fermentation temperatures, c) Wild type versus
 449 adapted strains, d) Pure sugar (glucose+xylose) versus hydrolysate.

450 3.3.2.1 Impact of temperature

451 During fermentation experiments, the yeast growth curve mostly exhibited a lag phase
 452 from 0 to 7 h and an exponential phase from 7 to 23 h. The elevation in temperature from
 453 35°C to 45°C caused the reduction in the P_b (from 0.031 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$ to 0.017 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$),
 454 but showed a rise in the μ_m (0.026 h^{-1} to 0.039 h^{-1}). Furthermore, the q_s was 0.43 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$
 455 at 35°C, 0.31 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ at 40°C, and 0.40 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ at 45°C. The Y_s^0 increased from 0.048
 456 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ to 0.105 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. The temperatures of 35°C and 40°C showed the 0.61 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
 457 bioethanol production, with the difference in time, i.e., 40 h and 25 h, respectively.
 458 Whereas, the temperature of 45°C produced more bioethanol of 1.88 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ at 40 h.

459 These results indicated that the yeast was not only thermotolerant but also produced
460 relatively higher bioethanol at higher temperatures. The fermentation time of 40 h was
461 found to be suitable for achieving a higher yield with 35°C and 45°C temperatures.
462 Whereas, 25 h was appropriate to obtain a higher bioethanol yield at 40°C temperature.
463 Increase in Y_{et}^O (0.09 g·g⁻¹ to 0.21 g·g⁻¹) and q_{et} (0.02 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ to 0.06 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹) also
464 observed by increase in temperature to 45°C. The Y_{et} were 0.84 g·dm⁻³, 0.63 g·dm⁻³, and
465 2.50 g·dm⁻³ for fermentation at 35°C, 40°C, and 45°C. A previous study by Martinez et
466 al. (2019) also reported high Y_{et}^O (0.12 g·g⁻¹) at the higher temperature of 50°C [63]. The
467 Y_{et}^O observed in the present study was higher than earlier findings by Martinez et al.
468 (2012), which reported a Y_{et}^O of 0.14 g·g⁻¹ by *H. polymorpha* from the fermentation of
469 sunflower stalk hydrolysates [56]. However, in comparison to *H. polymorpha*, the earlier
470 study reported very high Y_{et}^O of 0.46 g·g⁻¹ by *Kluyveromyces marxianus* yeast-led
471 fermentation after 72 h at 42°C of hydrolysate derived from dilute sulphuric acid
472 hydrolysis (130°C) enzymatic (cellulase) hydrolysis of extracted olive pomace [51].

473 3.3.2.2 Impact of inoculum concentrations

474 The utilisation of more inoculum concentrations from 0.1 g·dm⁻³ to 1.3 g·dm⁻³ improved
475 the P_b from 0.043 g·dm⁻³h⁻¹ to 0.050 g·dm⁻³h⁻¹. The lower inoculum concentrations of
476 0.1 g·dm⁻³ exhibited higher μ_m of 0.086 h⁻¹ than 0.029 h⁻¹ and 0.027 h⁻¹ observed for the
477 0.8 g·dm⁻³ and 1.3 g·dm⁻³, respectively. In addition, with an increase in inoculum from
478 0.1 g·dm⁻³ to 1.3 g·dm⁻³, the q_s reduced from 0.23 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹ to 0.06 g·g⁻¹h⁻¹, while Y_s^O
479 increased from 0.170 g·g⁻¹ to 0.211 g·g⁻¹. Guzmán et al. (2024) also reported that a lower
480 inoculum of yeast resulted in higher Y_s^O [85]. The inoculum concentration of 0.8 g·dm⁻³
481 produced 0.61 g·dm⁻³ bioethanol at 25 h time compared to 0.52 g·dm⁻³ bioethanol
482 obtained by a 0.1 g·dm⁻³ inoculum concentration at 23 h and 0.35 g·dm⁻³ bioethanol
483 obtained by 1.3 g·dm⁻³ inoculum concentrations at 20 h. The Y_{et} was higher (0.63 g·dm⁻³)

484 with $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum concentrations than $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ ($0.50 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$) and $1.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
485 ($0.43 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$). Higher Y_{et}^O was observed with the inoculum concentration of $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$
486 ($0.09 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) in comparison to $1.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ ($0.06 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ ($0.05 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). The q_{et}
487 gradually decreased with an increase in inoculum concentrations of $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ (0.04
488 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), $0.8 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ ($0.02 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), and $1.3 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ ($0.01 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$).

489

490 3.3.2.3 Wild type versus adapted yeast strain performance

491 In the case of pure sugar (glucose+xylose) fermentation, the wild type yeast strain had a
492 relatively higher μ_m (0.165 h^{-1}), P_b ($0.152 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$), Y_s^O ($0.320 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), Y_{et} ($1.50 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$),
493 Y_{et}^O ($0.39 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), and q_{et} ($0.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) than adapted strain with $\mu_m = 0.109 \text{ h}^{-1}$, $P_b = 0.104$
494 $\text{g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$, $Y_s^O = 0.198 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, $Y_{et} = 1.30 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$, $Y_{et}^O = 0.31 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and $q_{et} = 0.14 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$.
495 The adapted strain demonstrated higher q_s ($0.13 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) compared to wild type strain (q_s
496 $= 0.08 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$). In comparison with present results, previous study reported fermentation
497 of xylose by the *H. polymorpha* yeast strain showed μ_m of 0.05 h^{-1} , Y_s^O of $0.44 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and
498 Y_{et}^O of $0.08 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ [86]. However, similar to present results, another non-conventional
499 yeast, *Spathaspora passalidarum* was earlier reported for ethanol yield of $0.40 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ from
500 fermentation of $25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ of xylose with a $0.5 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ inoculum at 30°C [85].

501

502 In case of fermentation of hydrolysate, the wild-type yeast strain exhibited relatively
503 higher P_b ($0.057 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$) and μ_m (0.042 h^{-1}) than adapted strain ($P_b = 0.031 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}\text{h}^{-1}$,
504 $\mu_m = 0.039 \text{ h}^{-1}$). In contrast, the adapted strain showed more q_s ($0.43 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), Y_s^O (0.048
505 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), Y_{et} ($0.84 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$), Y_{et}^O ($0.13 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), and q_{et} ($0.03 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) compared to the wildtype
506 strain ($q_s = 0.10 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$; $Y_s^O = 0.296 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$; $Y_{et} = 0.51 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$; $Y_{et}^O = 0.11 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$; $q_{et} = 0.02$
507 $\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$). In a prior study, fermentation of clarified wheat straw hydrolysate (containing
508 $6.50 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ acetic acid and $1.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{dm}^{-3}$ total phenols) by the *H. polymorpha* strain

509 showed μ_m of 0.06 h^{-1} , Y_s^O of $0.54 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, and Y_{et}^O of $0.11 \text{ g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ [86]. These findings agreed
510 with the present study findings.

511

512 Overall, the growth of both the wild type and adapted strains of *H. polymorpha* were
513 found to be impacted by the presence of inhibitors in the hydrolysate. The adapted *H.*
514 *polymorpha* strains showed improved substrate consumption rate and inhibitor tolerance
515 compared to wild-type strains. In case of fermentation with pure sugars and without
516 inhibitors, growth of these strains started declining after 55 h. However, with hydrolysate
517 fermentation, these strains were able to tolerate the inhibitors for up to 29 h and afterwards
518 showed a sharp decline in growth. The inhibitor tolerance of *H. polymorpha* was short-
519 lived and dependent on the fermentation time. It is commonly known that the inhibitors
520 stop the growth of microorganisms by causing oxidative stress and cellular damage,
521 specifically by the formation of reactive oxygen species [87]. For the time period of 29 h
522 of hydrolysate fermentation, the *H. polymorpha* strains scavenged oxidative stress by the
523 help of metabolites such as superoxide dismutase, catalase and glutathione. Superoxide
524 dismutase and catalase are enzymes which scavenge reactive oxygen species and protect
525 yeast cells by maintaining cellular redox homeostasis [88–90]. Glutathione is a non-
526 enzymatic metabolite that functions as a major buffer for cellular redox and counteracts
527 reactive oxygen species [91]. Yeasts also possess the ability to detoxify major inhibitors
528 such as polyphenols, acetic acid, and furfural. The yeasts degrade polyphenols by the help
529 of phenol monooxygenase and catechol dioxygenase enzymes [92,93]. The cells of yeasts
530 can neutralise the weak organic acids like acetic acids by enhancing the generation of
531 plasma membrane transporters that remove the acid anions from cells [94]. Detoxification
532 of furfural by yeasts occurred by reducing it into furfuryl alcohol using NADH and
533 NADPH [95,96]. However, despite the inhibitor tolerance and detoxification capacity of

534 yeast, in present study it was observed that the presence of inhibitors has limited their
 535 capacity to achieve high bioethanol yield.

536

537 Table 1. Biomass volumetric productivity (P_b), Maximum specific growth rate (μ_m),
 538 Specific growth rate (q_s), overall biomass yield (Y_s^0), instantaneous bioethanol yield (Y_{et}),
 539 overall bioethanol yield (Y_{et}^0), specific ethanol production rate (q_{et}) for the fermentation
 540 of hydrolysate and pure sugar by *H. polymorpha* strains. Fermentation parameters
 541 included temperature, inoculum concentrations and strain type.

Fermentation parameters	P_b ($g \cdot dm^{-3} h^{-1}$)	μ_m (h^{-1})	q_s ($g \cdot g^{-1} h^{-1}$)	Y_s^0 ($g \cdot g^{-1}$)	Y_{et} ($g \cdot dm^{-3}$)	Y_{et}^0 ($g \cdot g^{-1}$)	q_{et} ($g \cdot g^{-1} h^{-1}$)
Hydrolysate fermentation							
35°C, 0.8 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, wild type strain	0.057±0.001	0.042±0.00	0.10±0.01	0.296±0.007	0.51±0.05	0.11±0.01	0.02±0.00
35°C, 0.8 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, Adapted strain	0.031±0.003	0.039±0.001	0.43±0.06	0.048±0.009	0.84±0.08	0.13±0.01	0.03±0.00
40°C, 0.8 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, Adapted strain	0.025±0.001	0.029±0.004	0.31±0.01	0.060±0.016	0.63±0.15	0.09±0.03	0.02±0.01
45°C, 0.8 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, Adapted strain	0.017±0.000	0.026±0.007	0.40±0.04	0.105±0.027	2.50±0.25	0.21±0.02	0.06±0.01
40°C, 0.1 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, Adapted strain	0.043±0.003	0.086±0.003	0.23±0.06	0.170±0.016	0.50±0.10	0.05±0.01	0.04±0.01
40°C, 1.3 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, Adapted strain	0.050±0.008	0.027±0.004	0.06±0.01	0.211±0.034	0.43±0.04	0.06±0.00	0.01±0.00
Pure sugar fermentation							
40°C, 0.1 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, pure sugar, wild type strain	0.152±0.005	0.165±0.010	0.08±0.01	0.320±0.015	1.50±0.025	0.39±0.02	0.25±0.06
40°C, 0.1 $g \cdot dm^{-3}$, pure sugar, Adapted strain	0.104±0.001	0.109±0.005	0.13±0.01	0.198±0.031	1.30±0.02	0.31±0.03	0.14±0.00

542

543 3.4 Process optimisation by response surface analysis

544 The coefficient values, F value, and p values derived from the second-order polynomial
 545 model (Equation 7) for response surface preparation and to predict optimum conditions
 546 for TRS yield, total phenols, and bioethanol are presented in Table 2. The phenols were
 547 found to be major inhibitors with relatively high concentrations in the hydrolysate and
 548 hence included for response surface optimisation, as it could be an important co-product.
 549 The high values for R^2 predicted (0.957–0.994), R^2 adjusted (0.915–0.988), F value
 550 (22.418–169.572), and low p-value (0.000–0.002) emphasised that the quadratic models

551 for TRS, total phenols, bioethanol were statistically significant. The TRS and total
 552 phenols production were influenced by the time and temperature. Likewise, the
 553 fermentation time and inoculum concentration impacted the ethanol production.

554 Table 2. Model parameters (based on equation 7) for TRS conversion efficiency and total
 555 phenols by conventional (C) and microwave (M) hydrothermal carbonisation, and ethanol
 556 production.

Parameters	C-TRS	M-TRS	C-Total Phenols	M-Total Phenols	Bioethanol
β_0	322.0	-310.0	11.0	3.34	1.06
β_1	-2.82	3.05	-0.106	-0.0203	0.666
β_2	1.12	1.55	0.0289	-0.0728	-0.0356
β_3	0.006	-0.007	0.0003	0.0000657	-0.526
β_4	-0.00456	0.00555	0.00172	0.00105	0.000292
β_5	-0.00454	-0.00778	-0.000469	0.000230	0.00194
P value (regression)	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000
F value (Regression)	170.0	31.5	90.1	22.4	135.0
R ² predicted	0.994	0.969	0.989	0.957	0.993
R ² Adjusted	0.988	0.938	0.978	0.915	0.985

557

558 Response surfaces graphs showing optimal conditions to achieve maximum yield of
 559 reducing sugars, and total phenols production are shown in Figure 6. Similarly, the
 560 response surface graph depicting optimum conditions for maximum bioethanol
 561 production is shown in Figure 7. The optimum conditions to achieve maximum TRS yield
 562 value of 25.92% through conventional HTC is 180°C and 30 min. In case of microwave
 563 HTC, the optimal conditions were 203°C and 30 min to obtain maximum TRS yield of
 564 27.88%. The impact of HTC reactor was evident, which showed that due to high pressure
 565 in conventional system, maximum TRS conversion could be achieved at lower
 566 temperature compared to microwave system. However, the differences between optimal

567 temperatures for conventional and microwave was very narrow, about 20°C. On the other
568 hand, the conventional HTC at 250°C for 2 min was predicted to be optimum conditions
569 to produce 3.29% of total phenols. For microwave HTC, 250°C and 30 min were optimal
570 conditions to obtain 2.85% total phenols in the hydrolysate. The optimum conditions to
571 achieve maximum bioethanol concentration of 0.59 g·dm⁻³ were 0.68 g·dm⁻³ inoculum
572 and 25 h fermentation time. Under these optimum conditions, the validation experiments
573 produced the bioethanol concentration of 0.53 g·dm⁻³, which was very close to the
574 predicted value by the response surface model.

575 The integration of HTC and the fermentation method adapted in the present work for the
576 valorisation of two-phase olive pomace slurry were effective for the production of
577 hydrolysate with high reducing sugar, phenol and acetic acid concentrations. However,
578 the concentrations of glucose, a preferred fermentable sugar for the yeast, were
579 comparatively low in the hydrolysate and could be the reason for the low bioethanol yield.
580 The application of the adapted *H. polymorpha* strain exhibited an enhanced substrate
581 (present in hydrolysate) consumption rate, but the overall bioethanol yield was found to
582 be 46 % lower compared to control conditions (glucose + xylose sugar and without
583 inhibitors). This highlighted that enrichment of glucose and inhibitors' removal from the
584 hydrolysate would be necessary. Therefore, the post-hydrolysis to enrich glucose and pre-
585 treatment of olive pomace hydrolysate with CaCO₃ could be applied to achieve higher
586 ethanol yield [54]. Alternatively, the future research focus of the integrated HTC and
587 fermentation method can be shifted to produce biochemicals, i.e., organic acids and
588 polyphenols.

589

590 Figure 6. Response surface plots representing the effect of temperature and time on TRS
 591 yield and total phenols using conventional HTC (A) and microwave assisted HTC (B).

592

593 Figure 7. Response surface plot representing the effect of inoculum concentration and
 594 time on bioethanol production.

595 **4. Conclusions**

596 Hydrothermal carbonisation of two-phase olive pomace slurry produced a liquid fraction
597 containing reducing sugars, phenols, acetic acid and furfural. Compared to the
598 conventional system, microwave-assisted hydrothermal carbonisation generated a lower
599 concentration of phenols, acetic acid, and furfural due to the lower process severity. Thus,
600 the reducing sugar produced by that method was found suitable for fermentation. The
601 hydrothermal carbonisation temperature of 250°C was found inappropriate for achieving
602 extraction of high reducing sugars. *H. Polymorpha* strain was able to grow on the
603 hydrolysate in the temperature range 35°C to 45°C and with high concentrations of
604 inhibitors. The bioethanol production was maximum at high fermentation temperature of
605 45°C. Xylitol was also formed by the yeast during fermentation through the xylose
606 phosphate pathway. The adapted *H. polymorpha* strains prepared by adaptive evolution
607 showed better substrate uptake rate in hydrolysate than the wild type. But the bioethanol
608 yield was marginally higher by the adapted strains compared to wild type strain. Overall,
609 the adaptive evolution was found to be a functional strategy to improve yeast strain for
610 more bioethanol yield production. However, it is necessary to conduct future research on
611 the neutralising the influence of specific inhibitors present in the hydrolysate to
612 substantially enhance the bioethanol yield.

613 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

614 **Adnan Asad Karim:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding
615 acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing original draft,
616 and Review & Editing. **M^a Lourdes Martinez-Cartas:** Conceptualization, Data
617 curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project
618 administration, Supervision, Writing original draft, and Review & Editing. **Manuel**
619 **Cuevas-Aranda:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Supervision, Writing
620 original draft, and Review & Editing.

621 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

622 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
623 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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637 **Data Availability**

638 For present publication, extended dataset with the title “Bioethanol manufacturing from
639 industrial olive pomace slurry through integrated hydrothermal carbonisation and non-
640 conventional yeast-based fermentation processes” is available under “OliPFUEL
641 community” of the Zenodo repository
642 ([https://zenodo.org/communities/101062601/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newe](https://zenodo.org/communities/101062601/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)
643 st). This dataset is published as an open access with Creative Commons Attribution 4.0
644 International license.

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